

**GLOBAL ECONOMIC FLUCTUATIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON
TOURISM DESTINATIONS AND PATTERNS**

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Abstract. This article talks about the impact of the global economy and its fluctuations on tourism destinations.

Key words. International communication, economy, development, tourism, division of labor, international production.

At present, the global economy is approaching a new phase of its development. After achieving integration, Uzbekistan has chosen its own path of integration into the world economy as an equal partner that respects its history, culture and traditions and fulfills its obligations to other countries and continues to do so. During the 33rd year of our independence, Uzbekistan managed to find its rightful place in the world economy. The results achieved in the development of our country's economy in recent years are highly appreciated by the International Monetary Fund, the World Bank, the Asian Development Bank and other prestigious international financial organizations.

Globalization is one of the main processes in the development of the modern world economy, and it is a high stage of the internationalization of economic life. As a result of the development of international division of labor, international cooperation of production, foreign trade and other forms of international economic relations, the interconnection and interdependence of national economies is becoming increasingly stronger. In the current period, it is impossible to ensure the economic development of countries without taking into account external factors. It is known that the increasing interdependence of countries' economies, the increase

in the influence of foreign economic relations on national economies, the active participation of large and small countries in international relations is the internationalization of economic activity. The internationalization of the economy has gone through a number of stages, the first of which is international economic cooperation, in which the role of foreign trade is extremely important. International economic cooperation is the regulatory and legal provision of international economic relations between countries, the process of reproduction beyond national borders.

The political aspects of the globalization of the world economy include the liberalization of the movement of people, goods, services, and capital across state borders, the end of the Cold War, and the partial resolution of disputes between Russia and the West. As a result of globalization in the social and cultural spheres, the importance of national customs and traditions has decreased, and international migration has increased. The emergence of a global consensus on the definition of the free trade system and the market economy, along with the elimination of the differences between the West and the East in this regard, led to the establishment of a unified view of the universal market economic system in their place. Education, art, culture and mass media are the formation of the globalized primary layer, the establishment of social, cultural, political and mutual relations through the English language, which is becoming the main means of communication, is a relief for the system of international relations. is creating. Distance

Tourism is one of the most promising and rapidly developing sectors of the economy. Neither global problems nor terrorist threats can be an obstacle for tourism. Because it has already become an integral part of human life. According to the World Tourism Organization, in 2019, the number of international tourist visits worldwide was 1 billion 460 million, while the income from international tourism exceeded 1 trillion 481 billion US dollars. 330 million people are employed in this field. Between 2009 and 2019, income from international tourism

increased by 54%. This means more than the growth in the world gross national product (44%) [6]. Many countries, including Uzbekistan, have recognized the tourism sector as one of the priority areas of national economic development. Because tourism contributes to the growth of GDP, the increase of foreign exchange earnings and the volume of investments, the development of industry, trade and social infrastructure. In today's world, tourism is an important sector of the economy.

According to the World Travel and Tourism Council, the share of tourism in the world GDP was 10.3%, the annual growth rate was 3.5%. The growth rate in this area has been higher than the global GDP growth rate for nine years in a row [7]. Tourism is an important locomotive of the world economy in terms of creating new jobs. A quarter of the new jobs created in the world in the last five years belong to the tourism sector. This is one of the few sectors of the economy that does not lead to a reduction in personnel with the introduction of new technologies.

Through its participation in the processes of the international tourism market, the country ensures the inflow of foreign currency and leads to the improvement of the balance of payments situation. The generation of income from international tourism also affects investments in other sectors of the economy. This leads to economic growth and development through the multiplier effect. Thus, in addition to the development of production, the country will improve its infrastructure and transport, communication lines, trade links, etc., which will ultimately lead to the restructuring of the economic system. In addition, tourism directly stimulates the production of industries indirectly serving the tourism market due to the demand of tourists for various goods and services in tourist destinations and diversifies the economic structure of the country by creating new industries and forms of activity. New jobs will be created in the tourism sector and in the sectors that indirectly support it, and they will reduce the unemployment rate in the country. Tourism develops market relations and establishes cooperation between various local

enterprises related to tourism, as well as between firms operating in other sectors of the economy. Often, such cooperation leads to the emergence of economic clusters

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